

Metal Complexes of N-Salicylidene 5-Bromoanthranilic Acid (II)

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N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilates of Cu(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) have been prepared and their possible structure discussed on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

The stoichiometry and possible structure of the N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilates of Fe(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) have been reported in an earlier communication¹. The studies on the N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilates of Cu(II), Cd(II) and Zn(II) are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid was prepared by bromination of anthranilic acid dissolved in glacial acetic acid according to the procedure described earlier¹.

Preparation of the metal complex: N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid forms solid complexes with Cu, Cd and Zn ions. These compounds were prepared by the general method described below with reference to the Cu(II) complex.

Copper nitrate solution was added to ethanolic solution of freshly distilled salicylaldehyde so that copper salicylaldehyde complex was formed. To this an ethanolic solution of 5-bromoanthranilic acid was added gradually with constant stirring. The mixture was refluxed for about 2 hrs. on a water bath. It was then filtered and the filtrate concentrated on a water bath for about half an hour. On cooling the solution a crop of green crystals of N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic copper (II) was obtained which was filtered and washed with ethyl alcohol. Complexes of zinc and cadmium, light yellow in colour, were prepared by similar method.

Preparation of pyridinometal complexes: The pyridinometal complexes of N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilates of Cu, Zn and Cd were prepared in the same way as described earlier¹ so that the water molecule in the complex is replaced by a pyridine molecule.

Stoichiometry and structure

I. *Elemental Analysis*: The chief constituents of the complexes—the metal, nitrogen and bromine in addition to water of coordination were determined by standard methods^{2,3}. The results are given in Table 1.

1. G. C. Shivahare and D. Shankar Rao. (Communicated).
2. A. I. Vogel. A Text-Book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry, Longmans, London, 1957.
3. A. I. Vogel. A Text-Book of Practical Organic Chemistry, Longmans, London, 1956.

TABLE 1

Metal complexes of N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid

Metal Complex	% Water		% Nitrogen		% Bromine		% Metal	
	Calcu- lated	Found	Calcu- lated	Found	Calcu- lated	Found	Calcu- lated	Found
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)_2$	—	—	3.39	3.32	19.35	19.31	12.18	12.09
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.48	4.43	3.48	3.41	19.92	19.88	16.29	16.21
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.01	3.97	3.12	3.07	17.82	17.74	25.07	24.99

II. *Molecular Weight Determination* : Molecular weight determinations were carried out with a semi-micro ebulliometer as described earlier¹. Molecular weights of the complexes are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Metal complex	Molecular weight	
	calculated	found
<i>Hydrated metal complex</i>		
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)_2$	762.88	755
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$	401.270	413
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)\text{H}_2\text{O}$	448.300	459
<i>Pyridinometal complex</i>		
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})$	462.27	478
$\text{Cd}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})$	509.30	520

From the molecular weights of Zn and Cd it is evident that they exist as monomers in solid state and there is 1 : 1 metal to ligand ratio in these complexes. However, the molecular weight of copper complex is double the weight of Cu ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{BrNO}_3$). From this it is clear that the copper complex is a dimer in solid state.

III. *Magnetic Susceptibility Measurements* : Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with Gouy apparatus as described earlier¹.

DISCUSSION

Copper complex : Cu (II) ion contains 27 electrons out of which only one unpaired electron is present in the 3d subshell. The Cu(II) ion and Cu(II) salts should therefore exhibit magnetic characters corresponding to one unpaired electron. The magnetic moment of the N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid copper(II) was experimentally found to be 1.86 B.M. at 300°K which confirms the presence of one unpaired electron.

N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid copper(II) appears to exist as a dimer in the unsolvated state as suggested by its molecular weight and may possess a bridge structure. Hence the non-planar dimeric structure satisfying the four coordination positions of cupric ion is

proposed in which delocalised carboxylic groups are involved. In this structure the cupric ions are far apart at the opposite ends of an 8-membered ring and therefore no direct Cu-Cu linkage is possible and so super exchange is prevented. The structure given below explains very satisfactorily the observed magnetic moments of the compound. Kubo and co-workers⁴ have found the magnetic moments of certain Schiff's bases derived from anthranilic acid to be 1.8 B.M. and assigned similar structures to them.

The N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilato zinc and cadmium and their pyridine derivatives were found to be diamagnetic. The values of diamagnetic susceptibilities of these complexes are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Complexes	Diamagnetic susceptibility -1×10^{-6}
$Zn(C_{14}H_8BrNO_3)_2H_2O$	4.76
$Zn(C_{14}H_8BrNO_3)_2C_5H_5N$	6.92
$Cd(C_{14}H_8BrNO_3)_2H_2O$	10.66
$Cd(C_{14}H_8BrNO_3)_2C_5H_5N$	12.74

In Zn^{2+} out of 28 electrons 10 occupy the 3d sub-shell. Similarly in Cd^{2+} out of 46 electrons 10 fill up the 4d sub-shell. Zinc and cadmium ions do not contain any unpaired electron. From the negative value of susceptibilities it is obvious that zinc and cadmium complexes under investigation too do not contain any unpaired electron and these are, therefore, diamagnetic. These complexes involve sp^3 bond-type and so possess tetrahedral structure.

4. M. Kubo *et al.* *Australian J. Chem.*, 1963, 16, 7.

N-salicylidene 5-bromoanthranilic acid is a tridentate ligand occupying three coordination positions in the metal ion. The fourth position is occupied by a water or pyridine molecule. Hence the following tetrahedral structure is proposed for these complexes where $M = \text{Zn}$ or Cd and $L = \text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$.

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